

Design of a PuO₂ oscillation experiment at the VENUS-F fast reactor

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804018

ABSTRACT

VENUS-F is the zero-power fast spectrum research reactor operated at SCK CEN, conceived as a neutronic mock-up for heavy-metal-cooled advanced reactors. The nuclear data of the key materials relevant for these applications can be tested through sample reactivity worth experiments. Since recently such experiments can be performed with the oscillation technique at the VENUS-F reactor. This study optimizes the design of a PuO₂ pin oscillation experiment scheduled at VENUS-F, computationally investigating two assembly designs—lead-based and fuel-based—and two oscillation locations—core center and periphery. The configurations are compared in terms of neutron spectrum, sample reactivity worth, and local perturbation effects. The similarity and representativity of the computed reactivity worth to the k_{eff} of ALFRED is also computed. The results show the design selection process based on measurement feasibility, response sensitivity to specific reaction channels, and relevance to the lead-cooled fast reactor applications.

Keywords: VENUS-F, Oscillation Experiments, Reactivity Worth, Plutonium, Local Perturbation, Similarity, ALFRED

1. INTRODUCTION

VENUS-F [1] is the zero-power fast-spectrum research reactor operated at SCK CEN. It is conceived as a neutronic mock-up for heavy-metal-cooled advanced reactors, offering an environment for neutronic experiments to tackle nuclear data needs for fast neutron spectrum applications [2]. Plutonium nuclear data constitute one of the largest sources of uncertainty in neutronic calculations for MOX-fueled advanced reactors [3]. Although a number of integral benchmarks are available for the validation and improvement of these data [4], additional integral experiments can provide valuable complementary information. This work presents the design of VENUS-F experiments with high sensitivity to plutonium nuclear data. In particular, sample reactivity worth ($\Delta\rho$) measurements performed using the oscillation technique are considered. These experiments offer high sensitivity to the sample nuclear data while reducing the sensitivity to the other materials of the system, and they achieve experimental precision better than 1% for reactivity effects on the order of a few pcm [5], enabling the measurement of small samples. This work precedes a planned PuO₂ pin oscillation experiment and aims to identify the optimal experimental configurations in terms of oscillation assembly design and oscillation location. In this computational study, two core positions — center and periphery — and two assembly designs are considered: one lead- and one fuel-based. The main design constraints are the experimental assembly integration in the existing core layout (identical outer dimensions) and flexibility to fit samples of various diameters for future oscillation experiments. The selection process is driven by the sample reactivity worth and by comparisons of its energy-dependent contributions across the different experimental configurations. The relevance of this experiment and the best configuration in terms of similarity to a target application is assessed by comparing the $\Delta\rho$ sensitivity in an oscillation experiment to the k_{eff} sensitivity of the target system [6]. The ALFRED reactor [7] is one of the most advanced concepts, conceived

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as a technological demonstrator for lead-cooled fast reactors, and is considered our target application. The reaction rate perturbations in detectors surrounding the oscillation channel are computed to assess measurability of local effects. Simultaneous measurements of global and local responses can be exploited to disentangle the contribution of different reaction channels [8] [9].

Section 2 introduces Serpent2 [10] models of VENUS-F [11] [12], oscillation assemblies designed with the PuO_2 sample, and ALFRED reactor [7]. Section 3 describes the computational methods used to compute and interpret the results. Section 4 describes the neutron field in the four experimental configurations analyzed. Section 5 presents the PuO_2 $\Delta\rho$, determined by the eigenvalue difference between the sample IN and OUT states, and with the first-order perturbation theory implemented in Serpent2 [13],[14],[15], which allows for nuclide-reaction-energy $\Delta\rho$ breakdown. The correlation analysis and representativity to ALFRED is presented in Section 5.2 and the local perturbation analysis is reported in Section 6. Section 7 summarizes the comparison of different experimental configurations for oscillating the PuO_2 pin, highlighting their respective advantages in terms of sensitivity, local and global response magnitude, and relevance to the target application.

2. MODELS

The VENUS-F reactor configuration of the CoRREx [11] and VALUE [12] experimental campaigns is considered (see Figure 1). The reactor core center (-1,1) and periphery (1,-4) are selected as experimental locations because of their differences in neutron spectrum, see Section 4. The two newly designed oscillation assemblies are shown in Figure 1. The first oscillation assembly features a square tube surrounded by a ring of fuel rodlets to maximize the fast neutron fluence in the experimental channel. A . The second is a lead assembly with a central cylindrical channel of 3 cm diameter. Both designs have a cylindrical aluminum guiding tube of the same dimension.

Figure 1. Left: VENUS-F core with coordinate system, experimental locations as purple squares and close-up of fuel and lead oscillation assemblies. Colors: 30% w.t. enriched metallic U fuel (green), lead (blue), bismuth (yellow), stainless steel (gray), graphite (orange), Al_2O_3 (cyan), aluminum (dark yellow). Right: PuO_2 pin axial and radial cut and Serpent virtual detectors around the sample in each oscillation assembly.

The sample comprises PuO_2 in Zircaloy cladding. The PuO_2 (62% ^{239}Pu) has a mass of 8.3 g, an active length and diameter of 5 and 0.8 cm, while the cladding is 50 cm long and it has 1.2 cm outer diameter. The sample is held in place by thin tubes located above and below, positioned inside and concentric with the cladding (not modeled). In the configuration OUT the oscillation channel is empty assuming the pin fully extracted from the core, while in the configuration IN the center of the pin is aligned with the active core midplane. A ring of 8 virtual detectors of 0.3 cm diameter surrounds the sample, in contact with the outer sample cladding (1.2 cm diameter), perfectly fitting inside the 3 cm Al guiding tube (see Figure 1). This detector arrangement is an ideal configuration that maximizes the local effect by placing the detector deposits in direct contact with the sample. Miniature fission chambers with different fissile deposits are envisaged. Accordingly, the local effect is quantified as the change in the ^{235}U and ^{238}U fission rates induced by the sample.

ALFRED is a lead fast reactor design fueled with MOX of enrichment ranging from 20 to 26%. It is considered as target application of this VENUS-F experiment. Oscillation of the PuO₂ pin would give a feedback on the plutonium nuclear data, relevant to ALFRED fuel data. The 3D core model of the reactor at Beginning of Life [7] is used to calculate k_{eff} sensitivities.

3. COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS

Reactor responses are calculated using the Serpent2 Monte Carlo code and JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library [16]. Standard k -criticality simulations are performed for each VENUS-F experimental configuration. For each case, the eigenvalue and local detector reaction rates are computed. Their change between the sample IN and OUT states represent the global ($\Delta\rho$) and local response induced by the insertion of the sample.

The detector volumes considered are sufficiently large to compute the fission rate variations with good precision. In contrast, $\Delta\rho$ calculations based on eigenvalue differences exhibit limited precision for small samples [17]. In such cases, exact perturbation theory [17, 18] can be employed, either through custom implementations in Monte Carlo codes or via the so-called Black Body Exact Perturbation method [17]. In this preliminary study, we rely on Serpent 1st order Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) [13] [14].

GPT computes the k_{eff} sensitivity to the sample nuclear data $S_{\Sigma}^{k_{\text{eff}}} = \frac{\delta k_{\text{eff}}}{k_{\text{eff}} / \delta \Sigma}$ where δk_{eff} is the k_{eff} perturbation induced by an arbitrary perturbation of the nuclear data $\delta \Sigma$. The integral sensitivity over the sample nuclides and reactions yields the first-order approximation of sample $\Delta\rho$. The reliability of this approach is discussed in [15] and reduces with spectrum softening because of the increased flux perturbation in the sample, which can be relevant in (1,-4). GPT allows for estimation of the nuclide-reaction-energy $\Delta\rho$ breakdown (i.e., the sample nuclides sensitivity profiles). This offers a basis for comparison of the proposed experimental configurations. Moreover, the sensitivity profiles directly represent the actual $\Delta\rho$ sensitivity to nuclear data and are used for quantitative comparison with the target application.

The cosine similarity C and the representativity coefficient R [19] — the latter being the cosine similarity weighted by the nuclear data covariance matrix COV_{Σ} — quantitatively assess the relevance of an experiment (E : $\Delta\rho$ of PuO₂ in VENUS-F) for a given target application (A : k_{eff} of ALFRED) [6]. The mathematical expression of the two quantities is:

$$C(S_E, S_A) = \frac{S_E^{\top} S_A}{\|S_E\| \|S_A\|}, \quad R(S_E, S_A, COV_{\Sigma}) = \frac{S_E^{\top} COV_{\Sigma} S_A}{\sqrt{(S_E^{\top} COV_{\Sigma} S_E) (S_A^{\top} COV_{\Sigma} S_A)}}, \quad (1)$$

where S are the calculated sensitivity profiles. In VENUS-F, only the sample nuclides giving appreciable reactivity effect are considered, while for ALFRED fuel, coolant and structural materials contributing to k_{eff} are included. The sensitivity profiles are scored in the ECCO-33 energy grid [20]. These figures of merit indicate how much the improvement of the sample nuclear data achieved from PuO₂ oscillation in VENUS-F reflects to the calculation of k_{eff} for ALFRED, providing insight on the relevance of the experiment in a broader framework.

4. NEUTRON FLUX SPECTRUM IN THE EXPERIMENTAL LOCATIONS

Figure 2 shows the non-normalized neutron flux spectrum tallied in the sample irradiation location in the four experimental configurations. The typical neutron flux spectrum in the VENUS-F core center and the core-averaged ALFRED neutron spectrum are presented for comparison. In location (-1,1) the fuel oscillation assembly causes an increase in the flux above 1 MeV and a reduction below 0.1 MeV with respect to the reference. The opposite occurs in the lead oscillation assembly: the fast flux reduces while the epithermal tail increases. In the peripheral experimental location the spectral difference is more pronounced. The fast spectrum component, suppressed in the reflector, is restored by the fuel

Table I. Total neutron flux normalized to the reference value in the core center.

Location	(-1,1)	(1,-4)
fuel	1.010 ± 0.001	0.398 ± 0.001
lead	0.955 ± 0.002	0.383 ± 0.001

Figure 2. Non-normalized neutron flux for the different experimental configurations. Reference flux is the typical neutron flux at the VENUS-F center. ALFRED core spectrum added for comparison.

oscillation assembly. The depression in the epithermal tail is attributed to capture and fission in ^{235}U and ^{238}U , with deeps corresponding to the resonances of $^{235}\text{U}(n,f)$ and $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ and (n,el) — e.g., the deep at 340 eV computed in (1,-4) is due to a $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ and (n,n) resonance. The energy integrated neutron flux is presented in Table I relative to the reference neutron flux in the center. In the fuel oscillation assembly in (-1,1), the neutron flux increases by approximately 1%. The leakage through the central hole is compensated by the additional fission neutrons produced in the fuel assembly, which contains more fuel rodlets than a standard fuel assembly. Conversely, the neutron flux in the lead assembly decreases by about 4.5%, as the combined effect of the removal of fissile material and the increase in neutron leakage. In (1,-4) the total neutron flux is about 60% lower than in (-1,1), with only a 4% relative difference between the fuel and lead oscillation assemblies, making spectral differences more relevant than amplitude ones here.

5. SAMPLE REACTIVITY WORTH

The PuO_2 sample $\Delta\rho$ in the different experimental configurations is presented in Table II. The calculation methodologies are in agreement within 1 or 2σ , with GPT always yielding lower uncertainty (up to 20%). This is the main advantage of this method, although its accuracy decreases when the neutron flux perturbation in the sample increases. As discussed in [15], a significant accuracy reduction occurs moving from fast to thermal systems. Consequently, the applicability of GPT for $\Delta\rho$ calculation is questionable in location (1,-4), because of the strong epithermal tail. The eigenvalue difference results are not conclusive because of their large uncertainty (≈ 1.5 pcm). The uncertainty differences between

Table II. Sample reactivity worth in (-1,1) and (1,-4).

Oscillation Assembly	Location	1st order GPT [pcm]	Eigenvalue Difference [pcm]
fuel	(-1,1)	4.95 ± 0.64	4.85 ± 1.44
	(1,-4)	1.79 ± 0.23	3.88 ± 1.44
lead	(-1,1)	2.82 ± 0.60	3.64 ± 1.50
	(1,-4)	2.03 ± 0.21	0.911 ± 1.50

configurations computed with GPT are due to the uncertainties of the individual reactivity components. The $\Delta\rho$ in location (-1,1) is significantly impacted by the oscillation assembly design (43% lower in the lead assembly). In location (1,-4) the reactivity worth is lower than in the center, around 2 pcm and the results across configurations are within 1σ . The observed differences among configurations can be clarified by the nuclide, reaction, and energy $\Delta\rho$ breakdown, which will also help identify the most

promising setup.

5.1. Reactivity Worth breakdown

The $\Delta\rho$ breakdown across the relevant nuclides and reactions is presented in Figure 3. The results are based on the GPT calculations and they sum up to the sample $\Delta\rho$ presented in Table II. The reactivity effect is driven by the ²³⁹Pu that is present in the PuO₂ (55% of the total mass) and the cladding, mainly in the Zirconium. The positive effect is associated to the ²³⁹Pu(n,f) and (n,el) in the cladding, with minor impact from ²⁴⁰Pu and ²⁴¹Pu(n,f). The negative effects are mainly captures in the cladding and ²³⁹Pu, and inelastic scattering in the cladding in (-1,1). In (-1,1) the $\Delta\rho$ difference between designs derives from (n,el) in the cladding. The large uncertainty of this contribution rises doubts on the significance of the

Figure 3. Breakdown of the sample reactivity worth into nuclide and reaction contributions (only if $\geq 1\%$ of the total)

observed difference, which was also indicated by repeated calculations. Overall, Zr(n,inl) has a negative effect, as it shifts fast neutrons below the ²³⁸U(n,f) threshold, yet above the fission resonances of ²³⁵U and ²³⁹Pu, resulting in little importance gain. This is less relevant in the lead configuration because the spectrum is slightly softer and the ²³⁸U(n,f) importance reduces. In location (1,-4) the Zr(n,el) yields the largest reactivity effect in both oscillation assemblies (~ 1.5 pcm) while the contribution from ²³⁹Pu(n,f) is about half in the fuel assembly than in the lead assembly, because of the different spectrum. In the lead assembly ²³⁹Pu(n, γ) causes appreciable negative effect. Assuming the validity of the presented results despite the limitations of GPT for $\Delta\rho$ calculation in epithermal spectra, the lead assembly in (1,-4) maximizes the plutonium contribution to $\Delta\rho$, although it yields the similar absolute reactivity effect. Excluding the impact of the cladding, which is planned to be subtracted from the $\Delta\rho$ by oscillating a dummy pin without fissile material, ²³⁹Pu(n,f) yields most of the reactivity effect in any configuration. The sensitivity profiles of k_{eff} to ²³⁹Pu(n,f) are shown in Figure 4. In (-1,1) little difference is observed as the energy-dependent $\Delta\rho$ (i.e., sensitivity) closely follows the neutron spectrum shape, peaking around 1 MeV and showing negligible contribution below 10 keV (see Figure 2). Conversely, in (1,-4) the energy dependence of $\Delta\rho$ sharply differs depending on the oscillation assembly design. In the fuel oscillation assembly, most of the effect originates above 10 keV, with only minor contributions down to 1 eV. In the lead oscillation assembly, the $\Delta\rho$ is largely dominated by ²³⁹Pu(n,f) in the eV region. 20% of the reactivity associated with ²³⁹Pu(n,f) originates between 0.54 and 4 eV. The ALFRED k_{eff} sensitivity to ²³⁹Pu(n,f) resembles the energy-dependent $\Delta\rho$ in (-1,1), although it shows a smaller contribution above 1 MeV and retains relatively high sensitivity down to 1 keV.

5.2. Relevance to the target application

The $\Delta\rho$ in the proposed VENUS-F configurations is compared to the k_{eff} of ALFRED for a quantitative ranking of the experiment output similarity to the target application. The k_{eff} is used for this compari-

Figure 4. Integral-normalized contribution of ^{239}Pu fission reactions to the energy-dependent PuO_2 sample $\Delta\rho$ in the first order approximation. The ALFRED k_{eff} sensitivity to the same reaction is shown for comparison.

Table III. Similarity analysis of sensitivity profiles between VENUS-F PuO_2 $\Delta\rho$ across different experimental configurations and ALFRED k_{eff} . Sensitivity vectors include either Pu only or all materials considered.

Experimental Assembly	Location	Cosine Similarity		Representativity	
		Plutonium	All	Plutonium	All
fuel	(-1,1)	0.89	0.81	0.92	0.69
	(1,-4)	0.91	0.79	0.79	0.60
lead	(-1,1)	0.87	0.83	0.94	0.71
	(1,-4)	0.30	0.27	0.42	0.32

son as it is one of the main integral reactor parameters. The results of the figures of merit described in Equation 1 are presented in Table III. The different columns correspond to different scenarios, in which either the sensitivities to Pu data only or all of them are included. The similarity according to both metrics decreases when all nuclides are included. This reduction is because many nuclides that determine ALFRED's k_{eff} are not present in the PuO_2 . The drop is generally more pronounced for representativity ($\sim 20\%$), indicating that the additional nuclides, although less relevant than Pu, have relatively larger uncertainties. In (-1,1), the two assembly designs have comparable performance. In (1,-4) in the fuel assembly the representativity decreases by about 10% relative to the core center, while the cosine similarity remains almost unchanged. This is determined by $^{239}\text{Pu}(n,f)$ as the sensitivities differ more in the region below 10 keV, where the uncertainty increases. When moving to the lead configuration in (1,-4), both metrics drop to 30, 40%, primarily due to the large $\Delta\rho$ sensitivity in the eV energy range, minimal in ALFRED.

6. LOCAL PERTURBATION

The ^{235}U and ^{238}U fission rates are tallied in the eight virtual detectors surrounding the sample. The fission rate perturbation due to the sample insertion comprises the local perturbation, see Table IV. The minimum and maximum perturbation, and their respective detector location relative to the sample are reported together with the average local perturbation across detectors.

In (-1,1) the perturbation is always positive. The ^{238}U fission rate perturbation is about twice that of ^{235}U and the effect is maximized in the lead configuration: the mean ^{238}U perturbation increases from 0.76% to 1.22%. The spread of the perturbation across the detectors is up to 3σ . Given the limited effect, measuring local effects in (-1,1) oscillating the PuO_2 sample would be challenging.

In (1,-4), local effects are more pronounced than in the core center. Here, ^{235}U fission rate perturbation is

Table IV. Perturbation of ²³⁵U and ²³⁸U fission rates in virtual detectors surrounding the sample. Minimum and maximum perturbations reported, along with the relative detector location (in parenthesis, see Figure 1).

Experimental Assembly	Location	²³⁵ U Fission Rate Perturbation [%]			²³⁸ U Fission Rate Perturbation [%]		
		abs(min)	abs(max)	mean	abs(min)	abs(max)	mean
fuel	(-1,1)	0.27 ± 0.08 (W)	0.61 ± 0.08 (E)	0.39 ± 0.05	0.41 ± 0.21 (SW)	1.00 ± 0.21 (N)	0.76 ± 0.07
	(1,-4)	-0.02 ± 0.33 (S)	-1.10 ± 0.31 (N)	-0.25 ± 0.19	0.11 ± 0.36 (S)	1.33 ± 0.36 (N)	0.96 ± 0.14
lead	(-1,1)	0.24 ± 0.09 (S)	0.62 ± 0.15 (NE)	0.42 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.23 (SW)	1.60 ± 0.23 (E)	1.22 ± 0.09
	(1,-4)	-5.47 ± 0.52 (SE)	-13.2 ± 0.5 (N)	-9.01 ± 0.95	12.8 ± 0.7 (SW)	18.2 ± 0.7 (E)	15.2 ± 0.7

negative because of sample absorption which significantly impact the low-energy part of the spectrum. The local effect is up to 1.1% and 13% in the fuel and lead oscillation assembly, respectively. The perturbations are asymmetric with larger magnitude towards the core (N). This could be a compensation effect of the back-scattering from the graphite reflector, more pronounced in the detectors facing the reflector (S). The ²³⁸U fission rate perturbation is positive and higher in magnitude than ²³⁵U, 15% on average. ²³⁹Pu(n,f) significantly enhances the fast spectrum. In the fuel configuration, this increase is less evident as fissions in the assembly already contribute significantly to the fast spectrum, resulting in a fission rate perturbation < 2%. Thus, the best experimental configuration to observe local effects is the lead assembly in (1,-4). There, the ²³⁸U fission rate increase is highly linked to the fission reactions in ²³⁹Pu while the ²³⁵U fission rate reduction is driven both by captures and fissions in the sample. A full sensitivity study will be performed to further investigate this.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the design of a PuO₂ pin oscillation experiment at VENUS-F. It investigates four experimental core configurations: two experimental locations and two oscillation assembly designs. Depending on the configuration, different irradiation conditions are achieved, from a purely fast spectrum in the core center, to a smoother and rather epithermal spectrum in a lead-based assembly in the radial reflector. This shifts the sensitivities of the sample reactivity worth and of the local perturbation to more epithermal neutrons. In all configurations the sample causes a measurable reactivity effect between 2 and 5 pcm, largely due to ²³⁹Pu(n,f) and (n,el) reactions in the cladding. In the reflector, the lead-based configuration guarantees higher $\Delta\rho$ sensitivity to plutonium with respect to the fuel-based although the comparable $\Delta\rho$. Experimentally, the cladding $\Delta\rho$ contribution will be subtracted by oscillation of the cladding alone.

Similarity analysis to ALFRED yields comparable results across all configurations except for the lead assembly in the periphery, where the similarity drops because of the strong epithermal tail of the spectrum ($\Delta\rho$ significantly impacted by ²³⁹Pu(n,f) in the eV region). Such a spectrum also results in large local effects, up to -13% and +18% for ²³⁵U and ²³⁸U fission rate perturbations, respectively. In contrast, measuring local effects ($\leq 1\%$) would be challenging in the other configurations. The core center, using either oscillation assembly, will be exploited for $\Delta\rho$ measurements sensitive to high-energy neutrons. In contrast, experiments performed in the lead-based assembly located in the reflector will maximize local effects and increase sensitivity to epithermal neutrons.

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